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“IMPROVEMENT OF ECONOMIC MECHANISMS FOR ENSURING RESOURCE ECONOMY IN THE FIELD OF COTTON GROWING IN THE AGRARIAN SECTOR

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Abstract. This article examines the processes of agricultural reform in the Republic of Uzbekistan, with particular emphasis on the efficient use of resources in the cotton-growing sector. The necessity of widely introducing market mechanisms, attracting investments, rational use of land and water resources, and implementing resource-saving technologies is substantiated. Under conditions of climate change, global warming, and increasing water scarcity, the effective management of available water resources is considered a critical issue. The study also analyzes institutional challenges, the role of the state in the agricultural sector, and prospects for creating a favorable agribusiness environment.

Key words: agriculture, cotton growing, water resources, resource efficiency, investments, agrarian reforms, climate change, economic efficiency, agribusiness environment.

Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqolada O'zbekiston qishloq xo'jaligini isloh qilish jarayonlari, ayniqsa paxtachilik tarmog'ida resurslardan samarali foydalanish masalalari yoritilgan. Qishloq xo'jaligida bozor munosabatlarini keng joriy etish, investitsiyalarni jalb qilish, suv va yer resurslaridan oqilona foydalanish hamda resurs tejankor texnologiyalarni tatbiq etish zarurati asoslab berilgan. Iqlim o'zgarishi, suv tanqisligi va global isish sharoitida mavjud suv resurslaridan samarali foydalanish dolzarb masala sifatida ko'rib chiqilgan. Shuningdek, davlatning agrar sohadagi ishtiroki, institutsional muammolar, investitsiya muhitini yaxshilash va agribiznesni rivojlantirish istiqbollari tahlil qilingan.

Kalit so'zlar: qishloq xo'jaligi, paxtachilik, suv resurslari, resurs tejankorlik, investitsiyalar, agrar islohotlar, iqlim o'zgarishi, samaradorlik, agribiznes muhiti.

Аннотация. В статье рассматриваются процессы реформирования сельского хозяйства Республики Узбекистан, в частности вопросы эффективного использования ресурсов в хлопководстве. Обоснована необходимость широкого внедрения рыночных механизмов, привлечения инвестиций, рационального использования земельных и водных ресурсов, а также внедрения ресурсосберегающих технологий. В условиях изменения климата, глобального потепления и дефицита водных ресурсов особое внимание уделяется проблеме эффективного водопользования. Также анализируются институциональные проблемы, роль государства в аграрном секторе и перспективы формирования благоприятной агробизнес-среды.

Ключевые слова: сельское хозяйство, хлопководство, водные ресурсы, ресурсосбережение, инвестиции, аграрные реформы, изменение климата, эффективность, агробизнес.

INTRODUCTION

In the following years, certain works are carried out on the reform of Agriculture of our country, in particular on improving the public administration system in the field, the widespread introduction of market relations, strengthening the legal basis of relations between agricultural products growing, processing and selling entities, attracting investments in the field, introducing resource technologies and providing agricultural products manufacturers with modern techniques.

At the same time, the absence of a long-term strategy for the development of Agriculture prevents the effective use of land and Water Resources, the widespread involvement of investments in the industry, the high income of manufacturers and the increase in the competitiveness of products.

The level of natural humidity according to climatic conditions is insufficient for farming and the full provision of livestock with a feed base. For this reason, the importance of the water resource in agriculture is also very high. The area of irrigated land in our republic is 4.2 million. over hectares, 90-91% of the total water resources are used in the agricultural sector. The level of natural humidity according to climatic conditions is insufficient for farming and the full provision of livestock with a feed base. For this reason, the importance of the water resource in agriculture is also very high. The area of irrigated land in our republic is 4.2 million. over hectares, 90-91% of the total water resources are used in the agricultural sector. Climate change, global warming, and droughts observed in recent years are causing a shortage of water resources. This is also reflected in the forecast given by various research institutes. In particular, according to the forecast of the World Resources Institute, by 2040 Uzbekistan will become one of the 33 countries with the highest water scarcity. The main task in front of us in this case is the effective use of available water resources.

Programs are being developed in order to diversify production, improve land and water relations, create a favorable agribusiness environment and a high value-added chain, support the development of cooperative relations, widely introduce market mechanisms, information and communication technologies into the industry, as well as effectively use the achievements of Science and increase personnel potential.

Economic mechanisms for ensuring resource economy in the field of cotton growing in the agrarian sector - are necessary to increase efficiency, reduce the cost of products and maintain the ecological environment. Innovative technologies, state incentives and effective management methods greatly serve sustainable development in the agrarian sector.

Decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 23, 2019 "on approval of the strategy of agricultural development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020-2030" № 1 of PD-5853 " on the creation of a favorable agribusiness environment and value added chain, wide introduction of market mechanisms in the field of cotton raw materials cultivation and cotton-textiles,, Paragraph 4 notes the rational use of Natural Resources and the provision of Environmental Protection.

The direct participation of the state in the supply of resources and the production and sale of products for farmers limits the attraction of private investment in the sector.

The village khojaligi has a great experience in the development of the Uzbek economy. The Republic of Uzbekistan, which is committed to reform agriculture in the years of independence in order to gradually implement economic reforms in agriculture and develop a sectoral economy, has adopted Nizomlari, decrees, decisions of the president of the Republic, decisions of the Cabinet of Ministers and targeted state programs.

Globalization processes have shown the need to fully take into account the impact that global agriculture has on increasing the competitiveness of foreign economic relations and Agriculture of our republic. One of the most important issues is the problem of increasing exports of World Agricultural Products, their release to foreign markets, coordination by the state. Globalization processes have shown the need to fully take into account the impact that global agriculture has on increasing the competitiveness of foreign economic relations and Agriculture of our republic. One of the most important issues is the problem of increasing exports of World Agricultural Products, their release to foreign markets, coordination by the state. Today, it is manifested in various forms in the export of agricultural products and is observed in all world regions, including countries with a developed market economy.

There are some problems that are affecting the effective use of the peculiarities of the territory in the development of economic reforms and agricultural development in the Republican rural Areas. Effective monitoring is not carried out on the dyeing of the reception clamping the implementation of decisions in the following vapors. Situations are allowed when the activity of farms does not fulfill the obligations and conditions established in the agreements concluded between enterprises and enterprises. In the conditions of the market economy, contractual monosubates form the basis of the effective management of the economic productions of the subjects running the farm. These problems are the mechanism of material curiosity in the activities of agricultural entities, the wave is not created.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Annex 1 of PD-5853 of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan[1]dated October 23, 2019 “on approval of the agricultural development strategy for 2020 – 2030”is dedicated to reducing state participation in industry management and increasing investment attractiveness in Chapter 2 strategy priorities paragraph 3.

According to the climatic conditions of our country, the level of natural humidity is not enough to engage in agriculture and fully provide livestock with a feed base. For this reason, the importance of the water resource in agriculture is also very high. The area of irrigated land in our republic is 4.2 million. over hectares, 90-91% of the total water resources are used in the agricultural sector. According to the climatic conditions of our country, the level of natural humidity is not enough to engage in agriculture and fully provide livestock with a feed base. Climate change, global warming, and droughts observed in recent years are causing a shortage of water resources. This is also reflected in the forecast given by various research institutes. In particular, according to the forecast of the World Resources Institute, by 2040 Uzbekistan will become one of the 33 countries with the highest water scarcity. The main task in front of us in this case is the effective use of available water resources.

Researchers interpret the nature and nature of the economic efficiency of agricultural production, economic characteristics, efficiency in the maturation of agricultural products in different ways. One of the founders of modern economic theory was A. Smith [2; 960-962-p] attributed productivity to the need for a division of Labor.

According to the data presented by K.Q. Shodmonov [3; pp. 597–604], agricultural production is largely dependent on natural factors and generates profit mainly at the end of the year, which makes it unattractive for investors. However, investments in services, as well as in the efficient use of land and rural resources in the form of large-scale, long-term megaprojects, can undoubtedly generate significant returns. Therefore, calculating the efficiency of capital investments in the above-mentioned production areas at the project development stage and gaining investors' confidence is of great practical importance.

According to E.A. Shkarupa [4; pp. 107–113], agriculture is considered a basic industry that is unprofitable and unattractive for investment, yet the growth of the entire economy depends on its development. If the state is interested in stability, a strong economy should support the creation of a favorable investment climate at both legislative and executive levels. Therefore, attracting investments into agriculture remains one of the key directions of economic development.

Investment in agriculture has specific characteristics. Along with capital investments in objects, as in other sectors of the economy, the results of human labor in agriculture are realized through natural objects. Their functioning requires long-term capital, has a longer payback period, and involves higher risks, since nature operates according to its own laws, which are either impossible or very costly to control.

V. Dobrinin [5; pp. 47–55], O.S. Libkind [6; pp. 48–51], K.L. Obolenskiy [7; pp. 192–195], and other scholars consider the efficiency of agricultural production as a political and economic category reflecting social relations associated with obtaining the maximum volume of output per hectare of land with minimal materialized labor costs.

According to Yu.G. Novikov [8; pp. 208–213], the efficiency of agricultural enterprises can be demonstrated by the systematic increase in the production of required assortments of food and raw materials per capita and per hectare of land. He argues that to ensure labor productivity, land productivity, and normal environmental conditions in agriculture, it is necessary to rationally use all resources and reduce costs per unit of output.

The specific features of agriculture—such as land being the main means of production, dependence on soil, climate, and weather conditions (seasonality of agricultural production), the difference between the working period and production period, the use of agricultural products in subsequent production processes, price elasticity of demand for agricultural products, and the large number of producers—create conditions for a highly competitive market environment. Compared to other sectors of the national economy, these characteristics require comprehensive analysis and consideration in forming the material and technical base, organizing production and management, and determining economic efficiency.

In agriculture, efficiency is often considered in close connection with natural, climatic, and environmental factors. Accordingly, the efficiency of the entire agro-industrial complex is based on the efficiency of using the natural resource potential of rural areas and the efficiency of processing agricultural raw materials. Economists classify the efficiency of the agro-industrial complex into technological, economic, social, and environmental types. Technological efficiency refers to the level of resource utilization in the process of expanding production. Economic efficiency reflects the degree to which production relations are realized in the presence of a certain production effect. Social efficiency is aimed at improving living standards, while environmental efficiency implies maximizing the satisfaction of social needs for food with optimal production costs, as well as fully preserving conditions for the reproduction of soil fertility and the environment.

Expected Results: Evaluation of scientific and theoretical approaches based on the analysis of factors affecting targeted resource use in cotton-growing enterprises of agriculture;

Development of practical recommendations for the rational allocation and efficient use of limited resources such as water, land, energy, and mineral fertilizers;

Reduction of production costs through the introduction of resource-saving technologies.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

The economic mechanisms for ensuring resource efficiency in the cotton-growing sector of agriculture are essential for increasing efficiency, reducing production costs, and preserving the ecological environment. Innovative technologies, state incentives, and effective management methods significantly contribute to the sustainable development of the agricultural sector.

LIST OF USED LITERATURE

1. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 23, 2019 No. PF-5853 "On Approval of the Strategy for the Development of Agriculture of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020–2030". Xalq so'zi Newspaper, 2019, No. 220 (7450), pp. 1–2.
2. Smith, A. (2021). An Inquiry into the Nature and Causes of the Wealth of Nations. Moscow: AST Publishing House, 960 p.
3. Shodmonov, Sh. (2020). Economic Theory: Textbook. Tashkent.
4. Shkarupa, E. A. (2011). Features of Attracting Investments into Agriculture: Current State and Development Trends. Published in: Bulletin of Volgograd State University. Economics, Vol. 3 (2), pp. 107–113.
5. Dobrynin, V. A., Belyaev, A. I., Dunaev, P. P., et al. (1990). Agricultural Economics: Textbook for Higher Agricultural Educational Institutions (Economic Specialties). 3rd revised and expanded edition. Moscow: Agropromizdat, 475 p.
6. Libkind, A. S., Ivanova, A. V., Litvinova, L. V. (1975). Agricultural Economics: Study Guide. Moscow: MESI, 48 p.
7. Obolensky, K. P. (1975). Theory and Practice of Agricultural Specialization. 2nd revised and expanded edition. Moscow: Kolos Publishing House, 192 p.
8. Novikov, Yu. F. (1978). Conversations on Agriculture. Moscow: Molodaya Gvardiya, 208 p.

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